

adaptability in Hubei, Hunan, Kiangsi, and Kwangsi Provinces (23.0-32.0° N, 107-120° E). It was derived by anther culture from IR8/Er-Jiu-Qing F₂ during 1978-88. The new variety usually ripens 3-5 d earlier than popular local variety Guang-Lu-Ai 4.

In regional large-scale plantation trials in Hubei and Kiangsi 1986-88, average yield was 7 t/ha, nearly 10% higher than that of Guang-Lu-Ai 4 (Table I). Hua-03 has better nutritional quality and palatability and higher milling rate.

An outstanding characteristic of Hua-03 is its high-protein content, especially of the eight essential amino acids (Table 2). Brown amino acid score (based on lysine) was 67% in preschool children and 89% in school children. □

Table 2. Amino acid analysis of Hua-03 brown rice.^a

Essential amino acid	Content (mg/g protein)		
	Hua-03 (mean of 5 analyses)	FAO/WHO standard	
		Preschool child	School child
Isoleucine	56	28	28
Leucine	87	66	44
Lysine	39	58	44
Methionine + cysteine	37	25	22
Tyrosine + phenylalanine	107	63	22
Threonine	32	34	28
Tryptophan	12	11	9
Valine	64	35	25

^aCompared with FAO/WHO suggested requirement patterns for preschool and school children.

elongation follows a complex pattern of inheritance. We studied the relationship between physicochemical components and grain elongation in 121 quality rices, including many aromatic types, during 1987 wet season.

The experiment used a simple lattice design with two replications. Each variety was transplanted in four rows of 17 plants each at 15- × 20-cm spacing. Normal irrigated rice cultural practices were followed. Quality characters were measured 3 mo after harvest.

Twenty varieties showed more than double grain elongation during cooking (see table). Domsiah (Iran), HR59, Basmati Maher 381, Muskhon 41, Basmati 213, Basmati type-3 (Dehradun), HBC5, and HBC45 (Haryana Basmati collection) showed excellent grain elongation, with the typical beaded appearance of cooked grains (see figure). Basmati Kamon, Basmati 370, Basmati 397, Basmati 43A, HBC30, and HBC34 also are promising as donors of linear grain elongation. □

Linear grain elongation during cooking of rice varieties in Hyderabad, India, 1987 wet season.

Variety	Raw grain length (mm)	L/B ratio	Cooked grain length (mm)	Elongation ratio
<i>With very high elongation</i>				
Domsiah	6.84	4.12	18.0	2.63
HR59	5.21	3.32	12.75	2.44
Basmati Maher 381	6.74	4.0	15.25	2.26
Muskhon 41	6.64	4.0	14.75	2.22
Basmati 213	6.76	4.17	14.92	2.21
Basmati type-3 (Dehradun)	6.61	4.15	14.5	2.19
HBC5	7.79	4.72	17.0	2.18
HBC45	7.12	4.44	15.42	2.16
<i>With high elongation</i>				
Basmati Kamon	6.89	4.26	14.83	2.15
Basmati 370	6.73	4.28	14.5	2.15
Basmati 397	6.74	4.34	14.42	2.14
Basmati 43A	6.37	4.0	13.5	2.12
HBC30	7.79	4.72	16.47	2.11
HBC34	7.08	4.53	14.91	2.10
Basmati 410	7.24	4.24	15.08	2.08
Basmati 405	6.62	4.0	13.67	2.06
Basmati 242	6.49	3.93	13.32	2.05
Pakistan basmati	6.78	4.14	13.75	2.03
HBC40	6.96	4.3	14.08	2.02
Dehradun basmati	6.99	4.29	14.08	2.01
Mean	6.82	4.20	14.76	2.16
LSD (0.05)	0.83	0.56	1.38	ns
CV (%)	5.8	6.4	4.5	8.1

Sources of cooked rice grain elongation

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Elongation of rice grains during cooking is one of the unique features of Basmati rices. Some of the key Basmati traits—slenderness, translucency, and aroma—R simply inherited and easy to transfer into other genotypes. But linear grain

Cooked grain of rice varieties showing high linear elongation. Hyderabad, India